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Supporting informed decision making by co-creation of a policy dashboard for the Drammen river basin

Judith ter Maat¹ Fatima Monji¹, Vanni Hermawan², Harm Duel¹, Trine Jahr Hegdahl³, Kolbjørn Engeland³, Hege Hisdal³

¹ Deltares, Dep of water resources management, Delft, Netherlands

² Deltares, Department of flood risk management, Delft, Netherlands

³ The Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate, Oslo, Norway

River basin managers and other stakeholders within their river basin have a collaborative need to better understand water resources availability under climate change and socio-economic developments. This is essential to be able to formulate effective actions to address the current and future water resources management.

The EU STARS4Water project consortium collaborates with key stakeholders in 7 river basins spread over Europe to deliver new data services, models and other tools. One of the activities is the co-creation of a policy dashboard to support informed decision-making.

The dashboard development within STARS4Water is a stakeholder-driven process: To co-create participatory understanding of the water system

To identify meaningful indicators in consultation with stakeholders In iterative steps co-design dashboards with end-users, for participatory risk assessment.

To adjust the initial set-up for the dashboard based on feedback from stakeholders.

To present results of risk assessments in dashboards and discuss outputs with stakeholders.

The information in the dashboard can be updated when improved data or more accurate models become available, without having to change the user interface or back-end database handling.

In 2025 a dashboard will be developed for the Drammen in Norway. This basin is impacted by changing climate like changes in seasonal river flow and more extreme high and low flow events. The socio-economic developments may introduce balancing potential trade-offs between growing agricultural water use and hydropower production. The dashboard will help stakeholders to jointly discuss such possible actions for improved water resources management.

The presentation and/or poster shows first results of the activities.